

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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MORPHOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF AGE-RELATED CHANGES IN THE THYROID GLAND
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Resume. *The importance of the thyroid gland for the body's vital functions is difficult to overestimate. Due to the wide range of thyroid functions and morphological changes associated with various diseases, studying its structure and functions is of particular interest to morphologists and endocrinologists. The thyroid gland is the first endocrine gland to develop in human embryos. It originates from the primitive pharyngeal floor in the endoderm of the oral cavity. The thyroid gland is the earliest endocrine structure to appear during human development, and thyroid hormones are essential for proper development, particularly for the nervous system and heart, as well as normal growth and maturation of the skeleton.*

Keywords: *thyroid gland, morphology, rat, postnatal ontogenesis, endocrinology.*

**ҚАЛҚОНСИМОН БЕЗДАГИ ЁШГА БОҒЛИҚ ЎЗГАРИШЛАРНИ МОРФОЛОГИК
БАҲОЛАШ**
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Резюме. *Қалқонсимон безнинг организмнинг ҳаётий функциялари учун аҳамиятини ортиқча баҳолаш қийин. Қалқонсимон без функцияларининг кенг доираси ва турли касалликлар билан боғлиқ морфологик ўзгаришлар туфайли унинг тузилиши ва функцияларини ўрганиш морфологлар ва эндокринологлар учун алоҳида қизиқиш уйғотади. Қалқонсимон без инсон эмбрионларида ривожланган биринчи эндокрин бездир. У оғиз бўшлигининг эндодермасидаги оддий халқум тубидан келиб чиқади. Қалқонсимон без инсон ривожланиши даврида пайдо бўлган энг эрта эндокрин тузилма бўлиб, қалқонсимон без гормонлари тўғри ривожланиши, айниқса асаб тизими ва юрак учун, шунингдек, скелетнинг нормал ўсиши ва етилиши учун жуда муҳимдир.*

Калит сўзлар: *қалқонсимон без, морфология, каламуш, туғруқдан кейинги онтогенез, эндокринология.*

**МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ОЦЕНКА ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ ЩИТОВИДНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ В
ВОЗРАСТНОМ АСПЕКТЕ**
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Резюме. *Значение щитовидной железы для жизнедеятельности организма трудно переоценить. В связи с широким спектром деятельности щитовидной железы и морфологическими изменениями при различных заболеваниях изучение ее строения и функций представляет особый интерес для морфологов и эндокринологов. Щитовидная железа является первой эндокринной железой для всплеска человеческих эмбрионов. Железа происходит от примитивного глоточного дна в энтодерме полости рта. Щитовидная железа является самой ранней эндокринной структурой, появляющейся во время развития человека, а гормоны щитовидной железы необходимы для правильного развития организма, в частности для нервной системы и сердца, нормального роста и созревания скелета.*

Ключевые слова: *щитовидная железа, морфология, крыса, постнатальный онтогенез, эндокринология.*

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Relevance. According to statistics from the World Health Organization (2023), 10 to 30% of the adult population worldwide suffer from various thyroid diseases associated with both dysfunction and structural changes. The incidence of thyroid disease worldwide increases by 5% annually. Currently, thyroid pathology, along with diabetes mellitus, ranks among the most common endocrine diseases [1]. The spectrum of thyroid diseases is extremely broad and ranges from minimal structural changes that do not affect patients' lives to significant functional and morphological disorders that reduce the quality of life, and in some cases, the length of life. The thyroid gland is the first endocrine gland to develop in human embryos. The gland originates from the primitive pharyngeal fundus in the endoderm of the oral cavity. The thyroid gland is the

earliest endocrine structure to appear during human development, and thyroid hormones are essential for proper development, particularly for the nervous system and heart, as well as for normal growth and maturation of the skeleton. During thyroid embryogenesis, the thyroid gland descends through the tissues of the neck via the thyroglossal duct, which originates in the cecum. The thyroglossal duct subsequently obliterates as the developing thyroid gland hardens, a process that takes approximately 7 to 10 gestational days [Polak M. 2014].

The thyroid gland arises from the ectodermal epithelium of the unpaired median process of the ventral wall of the foregut. Epithelial cells form a complex system of cords. Connective tissue develops from the mesenchyme, covering the rudiment externally and growing into it. The thyroid gland is located in the neck on both sides of the trachea, behind the thyroid cartilage. Environmental factors greatly influence its structure and function, leading thyroid pathology to be considered a marker of environmental stress. The thyroid gland has an exceptionally rich blood supply compared to other organs. Blood flow through the thyroid gland is approximately 5 ml/g/min. Endocrine glands, and the thyroid gland in particular, play a significant role in neurohumoral regulation, development and growth, age-related variability, and the body's adaptation to various internal and external factors. The thyroid gland has a butterfly-like appearance, with its wings formed by the right and left lobes, connected by an isthmus. The gland itself is composed of connective tissue and a glandular increting portion. The skeleton envelops the organ in a shell, from which a series of septa extend inward, passing between groups of glandular structures to form the lobules of the gland. Identifying the patterns and specific features of the organization of endocrine glands and the structural equivalents of their functional state is a fundamental problem not only in morphology but also in endocrinology. The thyroid gland is innervated by postganglionic fibers of the sympathetic nervous system. The thyroid nerves form plexuses around the vessels supplying the gland. These nerves are believed to perform vasomotor function. The vagus nerve, which carries parasympathetic fibers to the gland, also participates in the innervation of the thyroid gland. The thyroid gland secretes thyroid hormones. Thyroid hormones are essential for normal growth and development. They regulate heart rate and myocardial contractility, influence intestinal motility and renal water excretion, and modulate energy expenditure, heat production, and body weight. The thyroid gland also contains parafollicular C cells, which produce calcitonin. The hormone thyroxine, produced by the gland, accelerates oxidation processes in the body, while thyrocalcitonin regulates calcium levels.

The thyroid gland is an organ with a slow cell renewal rate. According to available scientific literature, the follicular epithelium in humans divides five times during life under physiological conditions. However, thyroid cells retain a high potential for both hypertrophic and hyperplastic processes throughout life, which can be activated by appropriate stimuli leading to increased secretion of thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Gazizova A.I. (2021) Histologically, the thyroid gland consists of follicles and a connective stroma formed of collagen and elastic fibers containing blood vessels, lymphatic vessels, and nerves. The structural unit of the thyroid gland is the follicle, a closed, rounded structure. The follicle cavity contains a substance called colloid, produced by epithelial or A-cells. In addition to A-cells, both in embryogenesis and in the functions they perform, these cells produce calcitonin, a key hormonal factor in regulating calcium and phosphorus metabolism in the body. Not only thyroid-stimulating hormone, but also other hormones, as well as thyroglobulin, cytokines, trace elements, and others, play an important regulatory role in morphogenetic processes in the thyroid gland. The processes of proliferation and differentiation underlying folliculogenesis are regulated by the paracrine influences of cytokines produced by both the thyrocytes themselves and other cells [Boronikhina T.V. et al. 2017].

In humans, thyroid morphogenesis includes differentiation of the solid mass of the gland, which occurs around the 10th week of gestation, acquiring a follicular aspect. Simultaneously, the tissue begins to synthesize thyroglobulin (Tg) and is capable of forming colloids and absorbing and incorporating iodine (I⁻). Fetal thyroid hormone production increases significantly in the second trimester of gestation, as the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis matures in the fetus during this phase. Thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH) is secreted by the fetal hypothalamus at approximately 8 weeks of gestation, stimulating the secretion of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) by the fetal pituitary gland. Around 12 weeks of gestation, the gland accumulates 3,5,3',5'-tetraiodothyronine, or thyroxine (T₄). The onset of specific thyroid function is associated with the progressive activation of transcription factors critical for the expression of the Tg genes: thyroid peroxidase (TPO), dual oxidase (DUOX), sodium iodide symporter (NIS), pendrin (PDS), and thyroid-stimulating hormone receptor (TSHR), which are essential for thyroid hormoneogenesis [4]. The HPT axis becomes fully functional only 1–2 months after birth [Kratzsch J., Pulzer F. 2018].

Citterio CE, Targovnik HM (2017) assess the role of thyroglobulin in thyroid hormoneogenesis. In humans, the thyroid hormones T₃ and T₄ are synthesized in the thyroid gland in a process that is critically linked to the iodoglycoprotein thyroglobulin. The general structure of thyroglobulin is conserved across all

vertebrates. During delivery of thyroglobulin from thyrocytes to the follicular lumen of the thyroid gland via the secretory pathway, multiple tyrosine residues can become iodinated to form mono-iodotyrosine (MIT) and/or di-iodotyrosine (DIT); however, selective tyrosine residues result in the preferential formation of T4 and T3 at different sites. T4 formation involves an oxidative linkage between the two side chains of DIT, and de novo T3 formation involves a linkage between an MIT donor and a DIT acceptor. Thyroid hormone synthesis is stimulated by TSH, which activates its receptor (TSHR), which increases the activity of many thyroid gene products involved in hormonogenesis. Furthermore, TSH regulates posttranslational modifications of thyroglobulin that selectively enhance its capacity for T3 formation—this process is important in iodide deficiency and Graves' disease. Currently, 167 different mutations, many of which have been recently discovered, are known to exist in TG (encoding human thyroglobulin) that can lead to defective synthesis of thyroid hormones, resulting in congenital hypothyroidism.

Changes in the thyroid gland of A/He mice during postnatal ontogenesis were studied at ages ranging from 1 to 547 days using morphometric and quantitative histochemical methods. During the first days of life, active organ growth, colloid accumulation, and an increase in the relative volume of follicular epithelium were observed, along with an increase in the intensity of histoenzymological reactions. During puberty, colloid excretion was observed, as well as an increase in follicular cell height with the activation of some of their enzymatic systems. Subsequently, during aging, follicular cells gradually flatten, the level of some thyrocyte enzymatic reactions declines, the relative volume of colloid increases, and its histochemical properties change. Clearly defined cystic changes were observed in the glands of animals older than 6-7 months [Bykov V.L.].

Smirnova T.S. (2020) examines the structural features of the thyroid gland under chronic stress in the early stages of postnatal ontogenesis. An experimental study has proven that immobilization stress in the thyroid gland of all age groups causes an increase in the size and area of follicles, thinning of their walls, disappearance of resorption vacuoles, and proliferation of connective tissue. Immunohistological examination with monoclonal antibodies against thyroglobulin revealed a decrease in immunoreactive cells in all age groups. Staining for calcitonin revealed an increase in the proportion and size of immunoreactive cells while maintaining an irregular triangular shape. A series of experiments in the older age group revealed similar changes, showing that under chronic exposure to a stressor not associated with a change in motor activity, calcitoninocyte hyperplasia develops in the thyroid gland of a growing organism. In the older age group, corresponding to the infantile period, there is connective tissue proliferation, and no signs of follicular compartment suppression were observed. Calcitonin staining did not reveal hyperplasia of immunoreactive cells. Quantitative assessment confirmed the observations at the qualitative level. When exposed to immersion stress, an increase in follicle area by 32.51%, a decrease in the height of follicular epithelium by 23.66%, an increase in the specific area of colloid by 31.7%, a decrease in the specific area of thyroglobulin-immunoreactive cells by 19.45% were obtained, and thyroid activation indices during immersion stress were reduced by almost 2 times. The number of calcitoninocytes increased by 35.69%. Exposure to chronic stress in early postnatal ontogenesis has an inhibitory effect on thyroid T-thyrocytes, which accordingly leads to a decrease in the functional activity of the thyroid gland. Severe pronation immobilization stress leads to Suppression of thyroid function. Using mild immobilization stress, a significant decrease in thyroid activity by 34.48% was observed in the infant group and an increase of 39.25% in the older age group.

The importance of the thyroid gland for the body's vital functions is difficult to overestimate. In addition to thyrocytes, the main cell population that makes up the gland's follicular compartment, it contains the second most numerous cell group—calcitoninocytes (parafollicular or C-cells). They are neurogenic in origin and belong to the so-called ARPO system, which is a collection of cell populations scattered throughout various organs and producing a variety of biologically active substances. These cells are considered a diffuse neuroendocrine system. Parafollicular cells are located in small groups in the thyroid interstitium and/or lie on the basement membrane between thyrocytes (intraepithelial), but never border the lumen. follicle. Their maximum number is concentrated in the central sections of each lobe of the thyroid gland, which are called the “C-cell region” [Hoff A.O., Catala-Lehnen P., 2002].

Parafollicular cells comprise no more than 1% of the thyroid epithelium. They are 2-3 times larger than thyrocytes, polygonal or slightly elongated, and have larger, lighter nuclei with 1-2 dense nucleoli and pale cytoplasm containing small argyrophilic granules [Pavlov A.P.].

The authors of the study note that the parafollicular cell population of the thyroid gland is constantly under the subtle influence of various age-associated regulatory factors, the vectors of which act in different directions. The balance of influence of these factors and their cumulative effect determine the level of functional activity of this cell population, the nature of its predominant hormone-producing activity (endo- or paracrine), as well as the state of the material substrate that supports these processes—the age-related mor-

phological organization of the C-cell component of thyroid tissue. A complex of morphometric studies revealed hyperplasia of thyroid parafollicular cells and a significant increase in their functional activity associated with age. Age-related dynamics of C-cell morphofunctional parameters reflect the body's need for their secretory products throughout life.

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